

CONTRIBUTION OF SCULPTURAL ART IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF TOURISM AND CULTURE

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Annotation: In this article, the contribution of sculpture in the development of tourism and culture, information about the origin and history of the development of sculpture, as well as the names of all the raw materials and tools used in this art, and a number of ways of making sculptures. is thought out.

Key words: visual arts, tourism, culture, sculpture, tourist resource.

Introduction:

Sculpture developed further during the breakup of the primitive community system in connection with the growth of the division of labor and technological progress. The most striking monuments of this stage are the Scythian gold reliefs, terracotta heads of the Nok culture, typologically diverse wooden carvings of people. In the art of the slave-owning society, sculpture stands out as a separate activity with its own tasks and its own way of working.

Literature analysis and methodology:

the correct and effective use of technical means arouses great interest in art in students, increases their creativity and activity. It is known that these, in turn, help to conduct training meaningfully. Also, educational activities conducted with the help of instruction help students to think, compare things and events, identify commonalities or differences between them.

Forms the skills of long-term memory of the subject. For sculpting, you should have a good quality pencil, a circular saw, various stacks, a hammer, an ax, a saw, carpentry tools, a drill, an electric saw, a perforator, and stone carving tools. The main goal of sculpting classes is to develop students' artistic culture and aesthetic taste through art, and to increase their love for art. Also, in this training, it is envisaged to develop the skills of students in working with various equipment and appropriate use of various materials, as well as the ability to apply theoretical knowledge and skills in practice.

Training is mainly held in special rooms adapted to sculpture. Art monuments found as a result of excavations - sculptures, jewelry, paintings, figurines of musicians - tell about the high culture of the people of that time. Thus, the famous terracotta statue of the musician introduces us to the Bactrian harp, an instrument of "heavenly music" in our hands.

Results:

The magnificent statues and reliefs of Khorezm, Sughd, Bactria Sughd, Bactria monuments, Afrosiyab, Kholchayon, Dalvarzintepa, Kuva created in the Middle East, including Uzbekistan, small figurines, and various art forms used to decorate practical art objects testify to the rich culture of the time.

In medieval Eastern countries, sculpture did not develop uniformly everywhere. The ancient sculptures of Central Asia are found in the form of wall-mounted, sometimes relief, but often

back-mounted voluminous sculptures. To a certain extent, this is explained by the insufficient strength of the basic materials. The main reason is different, only in an aesthetic sense. Synthesis of art was a leading feature of the artistic culture of Central Asia in ancient and medieval times.

Even the ancient Egyptians knew the properties of plaster and used it widely in architecture and medicine. Ancient Greek and Roman plaster decorations that have survived to this day represented the masterpieces of the time and set the benchmark for later architectural styles. Plaster bas-reliefs have been preserved to this day, depicting scenes from life, historical events and genre sketches reflecting the culture of that time.

Discussion:

Important tourist resources include structures of unique capacity - ehrsams, mausoleums, statues, temples, architectural objects, parks, museum collections, and high-rise buildings of modern structures and other large hydrotechnical structures. Also, tombs have been a tourist attraction for centuries, even if they look somewhat strange.

Thousands of ehrsams built in Egypt are the tombs of pharaohs and courtiers. Mausoleums are the most visited objects, some of them are included in the wonders of the world due to their amazing architecture and huge size.

Conclusion:

Sculptural art is different from all visual arts, it is done in volumetric forms. We know very well that the equipment of educational workshops at the level of demand, as mentioned above, plays an important role in increasing the effectiveness of the lesson. It is known that during the years of independence, a number of works given in the appendix can be recognized as the result of the tireless work of our artistic sculptors.

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